

**AS AN ASPECT OF THE QUALITY INDICATOR “DIDACTIC MEANS”
IN THE CONDUCT OF TRAINING IN HIGHER EDUCATION**

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Annotation. This article describes the analysis aimed at improving the quality of the training conducted in the directions of humanitarian education of higher educational institutions.

Keywords. Diactic materials, problematic teaching technologies, creative-analytical assignments, project-related teaching technologies, educational-didactic materials.

It is known that the organization of classes with the wide use of various technologies of education in the lessons, the productive use of disseminated materials taking into account the students ' enthusiasm will ensure that the lessons will be more attractive and interesting. The role of dietary materials in Bunda is great.[1] Didactic materials include problematic, interesting questions, creative assignments, projects games, crosswords and other materials aimed at developing students ' independent and creative performance and thinking skills.[2]

It can also serve as an example of the dissemination materials used by the teacher in the teaching process, cards, questionnaires, manuals, technological map for the organization of practical work, etc. Didactic materials in turn are also called educational-didactic materials. [3] After all, when we say educational-didactic materials, any sources of information that provide the necessary knowledge, which should be taught and learned, are understood. Text-visual means, which are used as educational - didactic materials in theoretical and practical classes, course materials in practical classes, methodical manuals, tables, catalogs created for obtaining additional knowledge and information on

science and conducting scientific-creative research, E-addresses instructions for the use of equipment or tools, in turn, are also included in the sentence of educational-didactic materials.[4]

- In the lessons, it is important to pay attention to the following when using didactic materials:
- Directing students to solve various problems;
- Orientation in carrying out various studies;
- Formation of skills to create and exit different situations and circumstances;
- Teaching different experiences and exercises in the lessons;
- Updates izlash and direct them to analysis.[5]

It is important to use instructional materials that ensure the independent performance of students in the process of training, especially seminar and practical training.[6] Examples of texts, projects and modules can be made on such materials. This is significant with the fact that the instructional materials are directed to the independent acquisition of knowledge and labor activity of the students.[7] Among the educational materials in our view, it will be expedient to cover not only the text of the lectures on the subject, but also the questions and assignments of different, volume and complexity so that the student will have sufficient knowledge and skills. Bunda taking into account the student's level of competence requires great skill from the teacher.[8] Competence, in fact, is the professional and personal qualities and characteristics of an individual, a criterion that includes knowledge, skills and experience of their application in practical activities, as well as the ability to work independently.[9]

In determining the levels of competency, it is important to take into account such criteria as the student's knowledge and skills acquired in science, intellektual ability, psychological characteristics, independent solution of problems, yangilik innovation, finding and implementation in practice, IJ

positive performance, ability to say and defend his / her opinion independently.[10]

In the tutorials, various creative assignments using different didactic materials can be combined with creative exercises, creative independent work, and also an example of various didactic games. If the knowledge learned through creative exercises is applied to practice, there will be opportunities to draw new conclusions from the evidence obtained, as well as to apply new methods of activity in the activity.[11]

When using didactic materials, it is recommended to observe the following rules:

- distribution materials should have a simple and straightforward look;
- in the content of the material (the text of the lecture, a text of something, a creative task, questions) there must be an important link between events and processes;
- in the process of completing assignments, the student should be able to draw from simple concepts, a more complex concept;
- it is important to create conditions and environment for the student's creative thinking. [12]

In the productive and effective use of didactic agents, situations that are organized in small groups or in individual forms are important.[13] For example, in small groups taking into account the opportunities and psychological characteristics of students ' mastering, and for individual work, issues related to one another on the topic of the problem, assignments, problematic situations are developed.[14] To perform them, specific instructions and recommendations are given.[15] When working in groups, educational characteristics and skills are also formed, such as the ability of students to engage in communication, to say their own opinion, to hear others without having an opinion, to actively participate, to respect each other's views.

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